

TEACHING SPEAKING IN B1 LEVEL

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Annotation: This article analyzes the methods, directions, specificity of teaching speech to learners with B1 level. The pros and cons of some methods are considered.

Keywords: Speaking, B1 level, method, student, learning.

INTRODUCTION

Learning English is a task that you can't just walk away from. Many students who have some knowledge of the language feel that what they've learned is enough. But in an increasingly competitive market, learning English has become a necessity. If you're already able to understand what others saying, hold are conversations, and even read and write some texts, don't miss this opportunity to expand your vocabulary and acquire greater skills. Establishing a Daily Plan will allow you to reach the B1 level of English faster than you thought possible.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DO YOU KNOW THE ADVANTAGES OF B1 LEVEL ENGLISH? Achieving an intermediate level isn't only important to obtain a university degree, a scholarship, or a job, but also to demonstrate that your knowledge of the English language qualifies you as an "independent user," according to the CEFR regulations¹.

In other words, although you still have a ways to go, your knowledge of grammar and the vocabulary you have acquired will allow you to address different topics, such as sports, holidays, health, free time, education, and jobs, among others. Similarly, you have the ability to hold conversations in English to express your opinions and future plans, to understand and elaborate on longer and more complex texts, demonstrating that you have a great command of the simple tenses, the future tenses, and the present perfect.

It is essential to keep in mind, when designing such speaking activities, that the activation of specific vocabulary and grammar schemata, which we, as teachers consider rather easy to navigate through, is not a realistic or feasible

¹Teaching the Spoken Language. Cambridge University Press Bygate, M. 2017.

goal implementation, given the fact that our students may not yet be biologically ready or intellectually mature to produce the desired results.

The third factor that should not be overlooked is the kind of [instructional methodology and techniques](#) applied in the English language learning process, meaning, educational tools and guidelines used in previous classes the students have attended, and the level of competency they were asked to exhibit. This signifies, that quite often, when we are assigned new students, we, as educators, have to place particular emphasis on the specific methodology we will choose to follow, and the frequency of application of those methods, to have the desired results in the speaking tasks.

The fourth factor has to do with defining who we are as teachers, by being alert, examining / reevaluating our strengths and weaknesses, acknowledging our skills and limitations, so as to make a valid estimation regarding the proportionate group of students/speaking class that we will focus on and engage with on a regular basis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TIPS TO LEARN ENGLISH AT THE B1 LEVEL

Practice your listening

To sharpen your ear and achieve better oral comprehension, try watching your favorite TV series and the movies you like in English. Listening to your favorite artists is also a great way to do this. Strengthen your speaking

Speaking with native teachers and students from all over the world will help you gain confidence. Take advantage of the live classes from ABA English and video calls to interact with English speakers.

Improve your reading

Short stories, articles on topics that interest you, and movie reviews are an excellent resource. Reading blogs like the one from ABA English will also be a great help because besides practicing your reading comprehension, it will help you expand your vocabulary².

Perfect your writing

Start by writing emails to your friends or teachers. You can also use this opportunity to write posts in English on social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter.

For teachers involved in the learning and preparatory process with students of upper- intermediate level, aiming at a B1/ B2 degree, the challenge of F overcoming persistent speaking difficulties can be viewed as quite a

² Ochilov, A. O. (2017). The Higher Education Dynamics and Economic Growth: The Case of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Management Value & Ethics*, 7(2), 46-53.

common occurrence. What is most important, when dealing with such cases, is to overcome the misconception that the only way to tackle with, and subsequently, resolve a specific speaking impediment is to focus exclusively on the organization and implementation of our teaching methods. Dealing, in reality, with multidimensional issue, characterized by We are a gravity pertaining to its characteristics and evaluation that needs to be assessed and examined in depth. Firstly, we should not disregard the social and situational factors in terms of the actual process and parameters pertaining to the actualization of the lesson itself, but rather, realize that there are unique and individualized circumstances under which the lesson takes place.

CONCLUSION

This goes to say, in other words, that if a student is influenced by predominant factors linked to family dynamics, such as health challenges and financial problems, the student will tend to be absent-minded or exhibit difficulty in forming correct sentences in speaking activities, because their attention can be often diverted to the above-mentioned entanglements. The inability to focus on the task at hand may present a regular occurrence, which persists, even if the topics are familiar to the students, or of particular importance with regards to aspects of their everyday life (general interests and preferences, hobbies, technology).

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